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THE ARAB GULF STATES IN BRITISH FOREIGN POLICY

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Abstract This article analyzes the role of the Arab Gulf States in British foreign policy. Historically established relations between Great Britain and the Gulf States significantly impact the political, economic and military aspects of the interaction between these regions. The article examines the key stages and directions of British policy in the region, from the colonial period to the present day, focusing on the strategic interests of Great Britain, including security issues, energy resources and trade. It also analyzes the factors that make the Persian Gulf region attractive to Western countries, especially Great Britain. The region has long attracted attention due to its rich hydrocarbon reserves and strategic geographical location. Britain's geopolitical and geoeconomic interests in the Persian Gulf play a key role in its policy in the Middle East. It is important to note that many countries in the region were previously part of the British Empire. After losing control in the mid-20th century, Great Britain was forced to reconsider its relations with the Gulf States. The UK's perception of the Persian Gulf as a strategically important part of the Middle East has prompted it to develop a unified geopolitical strategy for the entire region. Although the United States plays a leading role in the region, the UK acts within its national interests, seeking to maintain its influence on the world stage. The Gulf states have demonstrated a tendency to strengthen cooperation with Western countries, offering unique opportunities to strengthen their positions in the Middle East. In this context, the UK and the US have developed a consistent strategy to strengthen their influence in the region.

Keywords: Persian Gulf, UK, foreign policy, interests, oil, conflict, Iran, USA.

Introduction

Britain, as one of the world's leading colonial powers, played a major role in shaping the modern political map of the Middle East. The Arab Gulf states, including Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Qatar, Bahrain, Oman and Kuwait, have occupied a special place in British foreign policy since the early 20th century. The region has always been strategically important to Britain due to its geopolitical location, vast oil and gas reserves, and influence on international trade routes.

The Arab Gulf states play a significant role in the UK's foreign policy, being important partners in the economic, security and energy sectors. In the context of global changes associated with the transformation of the international political and economic system, the UK's interests in this region remain relevant and diverse, as noted by political scientists such as A. Gromyko and A. Baunov.¹ On the one hand, the Gulf states' wealth in natural resources, especially oil and gas, makes them key players in the global energy market. On the other hand, political stability and security in this strategically important region are of great importance for the interests of the UK and its allies.

Historical context

British influence in the Persian Gulf dates back to the 18th century, when Britain began establishing trade relations with local rulers. In the 19th century, in an effort to combat piracy and secure trade routes in India, Britain entered into a series of treaties with the sheikhs of the Persian Gulf, effectively establishing a protectorate over the region. These treaties cemented Britain's role as the region's dominant external power, a position that lasted until the mid- 20th century.

¹ Gromyko. A.A. - *"The Middle East and Great Britain: Politics and Economics"* . - M.: Nauka, 2006. - 74 p.

In 1968, having announced its intention to withdraw from East Suez, Britain ended its military presence in the Gulf by 1971, when the last protectorate treaties were annulled. However, this did not mean the end of British influence in the region. On the contrary, Britain remained actively involved in Gulf affairs through economic ties, military cooperation and diplomatic channels.

Contemporary aspects of British foreign policy in the Persian Gulf Today, Britain maintains close ties with the Arab countries of the Persian Gulf, based on strategic interests such as:

Security and military cooperation. The UK maintains permanent military bases in the region, actively participates in international coalitions to ensure security in the Gulf and regularly conducts joint exercises with the militaries of the region. The UK has sought new opportunities to re-establish and strengthen its traditional presence in the Gulf, in coordination with the US.

Britain's close involvement in the second military campaign against Iraq gave it a unique opportunity to ensure its military presence in the region. The United States provided significant support for these efforts. In January 2002, President George W. Bush accused Iraq, Iran and North Korea of aggressive intentions, calling them an "axis of evil." It was clear that the United States would not limit itself to statements, but intended to take real military and political action against these countries. Britain could count on close US support, and the joint accusations against Iraq focused on non-compliance with the terms of the 1991 agreement and the desire to create weapons of mass destruction.²

Iraq's failure to cooperate with UN inspectors further aggravated the situation, with Britain and the United States also accusing Iraq of supporting international terrorism. For Britain, this campaign was part of a general US strategy, and its main objective was to lobby for American interests in Europe. As part of this strategy,

² Davidson, K. M. From Britain to America: Changing Strategic Partners in the Persian Gulf // Middle Eastern Studies , 2008. - Vol . 44 , No. 3. - P. 55.

Britain strengthened its military and political presence in the Persian Gulf, interacting with the United States, which played a key role in the region.

Despite public protests and the lack of support from the UN Security Council, Britain and the United States launched a large-scale military campaign against Iraq. Britain actively involved Europe in this campaign, which clearly demonstrated the main directions of the two countries' foreign policies in the region. However, this campaign also highlighted the unequal nature of their cooperation, in which the United States played a dominant role.

Not all of Britain's expectations were met: Tony Blair's government suffered serious electoral losses, and the opposition used its involvement in the Iraqi campaign as a key argument against it. Nevertheless, the campaign was an important step in Britain's attempts to maintain a close alliance with the United States, which it believed would protect its own interests in the region.

Energy policy. The UK is dependent on energy imports, and the Gulf countries play a key role in ensuring stable supplies of oil and gas to the world market. The energy factor in the Persian Gulf region plays a key role in the world economy and politics. The countries of the region use their rich oil reserves as a tool to achieve foreign policy goals. Almost all states are aware of the strategic importance of the energy resources of the Persian Gulf. The Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) has become a powerful means of influence for the countries of the region on the world stage.³ Control over fuel and energy resources and their transportation routes directly determines the geopolitical weight of a state. Great Britain, after the collapse of its empire, sought to maintain influence in the region by controlling energy resources and transportation routes. This approach remains an important element of British policy in the region, but other global players are also actively involved in the struggle for influence. Not only Great Britain and the United

³ Zhukov. S.V. "OPEC in the World Oil Market" . OPEC (Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries) is an international organization consisting of 13 countries that are the largest oil exporters. OPEC was created in 1960 in Baghdad with the aim of coordinating the oil policies of its member countries and stabilizing oil markets. OPEC headquarters are located in Vienna, Austria , 2019. – 15 p.

States, but also other world powers are seeking to strengthen their positions in the region. The influence of the oil sector on the political development of the Arab countries has been significant. The struggle for control over oil resources and political regimes in the region has become a significant factor in relations between countries, especially in the context of Anglo-American competition.⁴The oil factor has also influenced the definition of borders and the formation of foreign policy priorities of the countries in the region, which has increased the potential for conflict.

Economic cooperation and investment. Unlike organizations such as the Association of Maghreb States or the Arab Cooperation Council, the GCC has demonstrated more active integration despite its smaller membership.⁵This has facilitated the integration of the Gulf countries into the global economy and the protection of their collective interests in the international arena.

Security also played a key role in the creation of the GCC. Iran's expansionist policies after the 1979 Islamic Revolution and the active presence of the United States in the region were additional factors for the unification. The idea of a federation in the region had long been discussed, but was only realized in 1971–72 with the formation of the UAE. The federation included Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah, Ras al-Khaimah, Fujairah, Umm al-Quwain, and Ajman, while Oman, Qatar, and Bahrain chose to remain independent.

Regional investment in the British economy, particularly in the financial sector and property, and the participation of British companies in major infrastructure projects in the Gulf are strengthening economic ties between the UK and Arab countries.

Political influence: The UK continues to play an active role in regional diplomacy, maintaining stability and resolving conflicts through mediation and participation in international organisations.

⁴ Mikheev V.I. *The Persian Gulf in International Politics: XIX - XX Centuries* . - M.: Higher School of Economics, 2010. - 8 p.

⁵ Malyshev N.I. *Anglo-American rivalry in the Persian Gulf region* . - M.: RAS, 2022. - 26 p.

After 2011, the world's attention turned back to the West Asian region and the Persian Gulf, prompting British leaders to look for opportunities to renew a direct military presence in the Gulf after 2012. The motivation to strengthen influence in the region remains relevant for British leaders today. We now need to answer the following question: What factors are pushing the UK to return to the Gulf at this time?

In fact, it can be said that the UK's presence in the region is a result of London's core political strategies, which support US policy in the strategically important Persian Gulf region.⁶

Today, the US is no longer recognized as the only powerful and hegemonic power in the international arena; the world now sees powers like Russia and China gaining strength and becoming key rivals to the US. Given that the US mainly focuses on economics in its international relations, Beijing, as a rising economic power, is an important competitor for Washington.

Conclusion

The Gulf Arab states play a key role in UK foreign policy, a role shaped by a combination of historical, economic and geopolitical factors. Throughout the 20th and early 21st centuries, the UK has consistently maintained close ties with states in the region, including Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain and Oman. These relationships are based on two main pillars: ensuring energy security and promoting political stability.

The political and military component of relations with the Persian Gulf is also extremely important for London. The countries of this region, located in close proximity to the most important sea routes, have strategic significance in the international security system. The UK, as one of the leading world powers, seeks to ensure stability in this region through bilateral defense agreements, participation in military coalitions and maintaining its own military facilities in the Gulf countries.

⁶ Panov A.V. *British Foreign Policy in the Middle East in the 20th Century* . - M.: International Relations, 2020. - 10 p.

These measures allow London to influence the development of political processes in the region and ensure the protection of its interests related to energy and national security.

It is worth noting that in recent years, a new trend has emerged in relations between the UK and the Arab countries of the Persian Gulf – the development of more diversified economic and cultural ties. In the context of global instability and increasing competition from other world powers (for example, China and the United States), London is actively working to deepen partnerships with the Gulf monarchies. British companies are seeking to enter new markets, including the high-tech, financial and tourism sectors, and are also participating in major infrastructure projects in the Persian Gulf countries.

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